

Mercurimetric Titration of Some Sulfur-Containing Organic Compounds

KRISHNA K. VERMA and SAMEER BOSE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur

Manuscript received 8 September 1973; accepted 27 August 1974

Procedures are given for the accurate and rapid determination of cysteine, xanthates, and dithio-carbamates in aqueous solutions by titration with mercuric chloride, employing diphenyl-carbazone as the indicator. Carbon disulfide is also estimated by quantitative conversion to xanthate and titration of the latter. Results were reproducible within 0.3% and accurate to 0.5% for the titration of xanthates and dithiocarbamates and 2% low when cysteine was being determined.

KOLTHOFF¹ *et al.*, from polarographic studies of the reaction of mercuric mercury with reduced glutathione and with cysteine have found that this reaction can be made the basis of a mercurimetric titration of sulfhydryl groups in biological materials. They also noted that in the determination of glutathione and sulfhydryl in proteins the mercurimetric titration is much more accurate than the argentimetric one²⁻³.

Przybylowicz and Rogers⁴ determined the sulfhydryl group coulometrically with electrogenerated Hg(II). Mercaptans were titrated in neutral acetone or aqueous solution by titration with mercuric perchlorate, when the end point may be detected visually with thio-Michler's ketone⁵. *o*-Hydroxy-mercuribenzoate with dithiofluorescein as indicator⁶⁻⁷ and *p*(dimethyl- or diethylamino-) phenylmercuri-acetate with diphenylcarbazone⁸, have been employed for the titration of thiols. Veibel and Wronski⁹ used *o*-hydroxymercuribenzoate as titrant and dithiofluorescein as indicator for the estimation of xanthates, whereas Kekedy and Makkay¹⁰ determined potassium ethylxanthate using mercuric acetate, diphenylcarbazone being served to indicate the end point. Gregg *et al.*¹¹, using mercuric nitrate as titrant and diphenylcarbazone as indicator for determining mercaptans have shown that the method is reproducible within 2.5%. The detection of the end point was probably the largest source of error. Roberts¹² reported that only alkaline form of the indicator diphenylcarbazone gives the deep blue-violet complex with mercury (II) ion.

The present study deals with the titration of cysteine, xanthates, and dithiocarbamates in aqueous solutions with mercuric chloride, using diphenyl-carbazone as indicator. The basic reaction for the mercurimetric titration of cysteine is the formation of the mercaptide in which one mercury atom is

present per sulfhydryl group,

titrations were performed in pyridine buffered medium.

Sodium or potassium salts of xanthates and dithiocarbamates were titrated in aqueous solution, and were found to react respectively as,

and

The titration of xanthates has been applied to the determination of carbon disulfide, involving conversion to xanthate with potassium ethoxide and then titration with mercuric chloride

Diphenylcarbazone was successfully used in these titrations, the colour change being noted within a drop of the titrant.

Experimental

Reagent and Samples

Mercuric chloride was E. Merck's grade analytical reagent; a stock solution of it, 0.05M, was prepared by dissolving a right amount of sample in distilled water. Less concentrated solutions were made by diluting the stock solution.

Cysteine hydrochloride and dithiocarbamates were commercially available samples. Xanthates were prepared¹³ by the authors and were recrystallized from the alcohol from which they were synthesized. Carbon disulfide and all other reagents were C.P.

Diphenylcarbazone indicator, 0.5% in 95% ethanol, was used; due to deterioration a fresh solution was always employed.

* Present address : 310, Napier Town, Jabalpur (M.P.).

Procedure for determining cysteine

To 20–25 ml of an aqueous solution containing 0.1–1.0 mmole of cysteine, 1 ml of pyridine and 3–6 drops of diphenylcarbazone indicator, were added; the solution titrated with 0.025M mercuric chloride solution to the colour change from orange-red to blue-violet. The end point is sharp within one drop of the reagent.

Procedure for determining xanthates and dithiocarbamates

A sample containing 0.05–1.0 mmole of sodium or potassium salt of xanthate or dithiocarbamate was dissolved in 50 ml of water and to it about 0.5 ml of diphenylcarbazone indicator was added; it was titrated with 0.01M mercuric chloride solution, while shaking the solution vigorously. At the end point, the colour changes from orange-red to blue-violet. Mercury salts get precipitated during the titration but do not hamper detection of end point.

Procedure for determining carbon disulfide

A sample, containing 0.1–1.0 mmole of carbon disulfide, was weighed in a small glass bulb and broken beneath the surface of 5 ml of absolute ethanol having 0.5–2.0 ml of 10% absolute ethanolic potassium hydroxide, contained in a 150 ml flask. A sharp rap against the side of the flask was sufficient to break the bulb and to release the sample. Contents were swirled for 2 mins, then diluted with 50 ml of water. About 0.5 ml of diphenylcarbazone indicator was added and the xanthate formed titrated with 0.01M mercuric chloride solution to a blue-violet colour.

Results

In Table 1, results are given for the determination of purity of carbon disulfide, cysteine, dithiocarbamates, and xanthates. As a check, carbon disulfide was determined by conversion to xanthate and then titration with iodine¹⁴, cysteine by oxidation with *o*-iodosobenzoate^{15–16}, and xanthates and dithiocarbamates by iodimetric¹⁷ and total sulfur analysis; the results obtained are compared in Table 1.

Carbon disulfide, dithiocarbamates, and xanthates can be accurately titrated with mercuric chloride. Cysteine yields low results, so an empirical correction of +2% is necessary. No sharp end point was observed when other mercaptans were titrated under condition used for determining cysteine. Treatment of the mercaptan sample with an excess of mercuric chloride, then back determination by adding a known excess of cysteine followed by titration with mercuric chloride, also failed due to non-evident colour change with diphenylcarbazone indicator. Water-methanol and water-ethanol mixed solvents having less than 50% of the alcohol may be used. Chloride ions, when present in large amounts, reduce the sharpness of the end point.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Prof. G. S. Misra, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing necessary laboratory facilities.

References

1. I. M. KOLTHOFF, W. STRICKS and L. MOBRÉN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 366.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and W. STRICKS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1952.
3. N. WEISSMAN, E. B. SCHOENBACH and E. B. ARMISTEAD, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1950, 187, 153.
4. E. P. PRZYBYLOWICZ and L. B. ROGERS, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, 18, 596.
5. J. S. FRITZ and T. A. PALMER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 98.
6. M. WRONSKI, *Chemia Analit.*, 1961, 6, 859.
7. M. WRONSKI, *Analyst*, 1964, 89, 800.
8. C. A. BROWN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 39, 1882.
9. S. VEIBEL and M. WRONSKI, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1966, 20, 849. *
10. L. KEKEDY and E. MAKKAY, *Studia. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai*, 1964, 9, 55.
11. D. C. GREGG, P. E. BOUFFORD and R. BARTON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 269.
12. I. ROBERTS, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1936, 8, 365.
13. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry*, Longman, London, E. L. B. S. Edn., 1968, p. 499.
14. M. P. MATUSZAK, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1932, 4, 98.
15. L. HELLERMAN, F. P. CHINARD and P. A. RAMSDELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2551.
16. K. K. VERMA and S. BOSE, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1974, 70, 227.
17. A. L. LINCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 203.

TABLE 1.—MERCURIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF SOME SULFUR-CONTAINING ORGANIC COMPOUNDS

Sample	Purity ^a , %		
	Mercury (II) titration	Iodimetry	Total sulfur analysis
Carbon disulfide	92.8	93.5	—
Cysteine ^b	97.8	—	—
Na di-ethyldithiocarbamate	78.2	79.8	82.1 ^c
Na di-isopropyldithiocarbamate	88.2	87.5	88.7
Na di- <i>n</i> -butyldithiocarbamate	90.5	91.3	95.0 ^c
Na di-amylidithiocarbamate	93.2	93.9	94.1
Na phenylethyldithiocarbamate	80.9	81.4	90.5 ^c
Na <i>n</i> -propylxanthate	98.9	99.1	99.0
K <i>n</i> -butylxanthate	94.5	93.8	94.6
K amylxanthate	98.3	97.1	97.5
K allylxanthate	94.9	94.2	95.3
K isopropylxanthate	79.3	79.1	78.8
Na ethylxanthate	90.4	90.2	89.9
K cyclohexylxanthate	97.0	96.4	96.2
K sec-butylxanthate	99.8	99.1	99.6
K isocamylxanthate	94.5	94.3	95.0

^a av. of 6 determinations.

^b purity determined by *o*-iodosobenzoate method = 99.7%.

^c high results based on total sulfur analysis are due to the presence of thiuram derivative.